

**ADVANCED FOREIGN METHODOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF
PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE IN THE MANAGEMENT OF INSTITUTIONS OF
PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION**

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Abstract. *A group of instructors, instructional aids, students, and instructional technologies make up the formal framework of the higher education system's professional pedagogical training program. The significance of enhancing teachers' professional competency is covered in this article.*

Keywords: *pedagogue, teaching technologies, professional pedagogical activity, creativity, curiosity, attentiveness, and professional competence.*

Аннотация. *Группа преподавателей, учебные пособия, студенты и технологии обучения составляют формальную основу программы профессиональной педагогической подготовки в системе высшего образования. В этой статье рассматривается важность повышения профессиональной компетентности учителей.*

Ключевые слова: *педагог, технологии обучения, профессиональная педагогическая деятельность, креативность, любознательность, внимательность, профессиональная компетентность.*

Annotatsiya. *O‘qituvchilar, o‘quv qo‘llanmalari, talabalar va o‘qitish texnologiyalari oliy ta’lim tizimining kasbiy pedagogik kadrlar tayyorlash dasturining rasmiy asosini tashkil qiladi. O‘qituvchilarning kasbiy malakasini oshirishning ahamiyati ushbu maqolada yoritilgan.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *pedagog, o‘qitish texnologiyalari, kasbiy pedagogik faoliyat, ijodkorlik, qiziquvchanlik, diqqat va kasbiy kompetentsiya.*

Processes of training highly qualified pedagogic personnel that meet the requirements of the time are currently the main demand of the international labor market. The reason for this is that free-thinking, self-expressive, and objectively self-assessed people are very important in society. They are the movers of the development of society. This, in its place, makes a great contribution to the development of the professional competence of specialists and renews the content of education, bringing about the need for the wide implementation of innovative forms and methods of teaching, advanced foreign experiences in teaching modern information and communication technologies. emits In this regard, a number of measures are currently being implemented in educational institutions to further improve the quality of education, to ensure the coherence and continuity of educational courses. In addition, the concept of competence is also important in the characteristics of the development of professional competence in future pedagogues. Competence - requires constant enrichment of one's knowledge and skills, learning new information, feeling the demands of the current era, the ability to find new knowledge, process it and apply it during one's work. It is worth noting that modernization of the educational process in educational institutions, raising the professional competence of pedagogues in further improving the quality level of the system of training of pedagogues, using modern and advanced foreign experiences in the field to provide them with professional knowledge, skills and experience One

of the important tasks is to arm with skills, to be able to use scientific and technical innovations independently, and to further develop the skills to solve promising tasks. In this regard, it is important to pay special attention to the professional competence of future teachers and their analytical skills. Since the basis of competence consists of abilities, each of them should correspond to their own competence.

Today, the term "professional competence" is often used. Competence is defined in explanatory dictionaries as understanding and knowledge. When translated from Latin, "competent" denotes a series of issues in which a person is educated, has knowledge and experience. Latin: compete-I achieve, obey, approach. In a word, professional competence is the ability to transform knowledge, skills and skills into practice. Professional competencies are the ability to perform professional tasks or a specific professional task. It is assumed that you will be able to do the work efficiently and achieve the desired result. Also, the following types of competence are distinguished: - individual competence: personal characteristics that help promote yourself and achieve results. - leadership skills: leadership, not Management. Because not all leaders can be leaders, not everyone can be leaders. This is more about how much a person can lead or guide the development of an individual and an expert. - functional competencies. Refers only to the field of human activity. - social competence: includes cognitive and behavioral abilities within a social group. - emotional competence: the ability to analyze your strengths and weaknesses to which emotional intelligence is responsible. Professional competence and professional self-awareness is a lifelong process, a person chooses a professional from the stages of dreaming, testing, choosing and their implementation, and then enters the profession, which then changes his profession or specialty, depending on the change in professions in the world, changes in himself, his attitude to work. Professional competence is again understood as complex integral education, including a set of knowledge of professional importance. Skills and abilities, personal qualities, certain ways of thinking and a certain degree of responsibility for one's own actions are understood. An important role in the image of a modern teacher is played by the embodiment of perfection. Today, the development of professional competence of the teacher consists in increasing his daily competence, productivity of the work process. It is possible to train qualified specialists by studying and solving problems associated with the formation of professional skills in work activities, forming professional training. The need to improve the pedagogical-psychological knowledge, skills of future teachers is justified by the growth of social requirements imposed on the educational institution and teachers. In the field of higher education, it is carried out to determine the level of their professional training, determine the aspects that meet the requirements in it and the actual needs for education based on the identification of existing shortcomings and gaps. Based on this, it is advisable to introduce innovations into life. This leads to the development of pedagogical competence. Another of the situations that are important during the training sessions is the organization of students' learning processes based on their needs and the focus on the personality of the student. These include the interests of students to know, the sense of duty in them, as well as the methods of forming a sense of responsibility in the educational process.

Acting in the direction of training competitive, qualified personnel corresponding to the requirements of the world, the correct attitude of the future generation to high morale, changes in social life, the education of competent individuals who deeply understand the essence of our national values, the teacher should show the values of creativity, research, dedication. The teacher

should also have skills and art that he should be able to attract students, make his lesson interesting and give the student knowledge and upbringing. One of our main tasks now is to teach students to effectively apply the various types of qualifications that they occupy in situations found in their personal, professional and social life, to independently teach, to independently seek out the necessary information regarding science, to be able to distinguish materials on the increase in necessary knowledge from analysis, inconclusive, that is, it consists in giving special importance to the qualifications that give work when problem situations arise, as well as in educating the acquisition of characteristics that can apply the acquired knowledge in the process of their daily life. Competencies should also be formed in students in the upbringing of these features, especially in combination with the absorption of knowledge, skills and abilities in the course of the lesson related to the native language and literature.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The formal structure of the system of professional pedagogical training in a higher educational institution will consist of a complex of teachers, educational tools, students, as well as teaching technologies. The formation of professional pedagogical competence of teachers in a higher educational institution involves the following processes: the main purpose of the formation of professional competence of the future teacher is to train mature, qualified personnel. According to the ideas of a particular discipline from students studying in the areas of pedagogical education of this, that is, the humanitarian sphere, in accordance with state educational standards. In the state educational standard, the graduate in his professional pedagogical activity is teaching, upbringing, educational and methodological production, it is envisaged to operate in research tasks. Qualified educational process is organized using educational content (DTS and educational plan, programs), form, method, tools (textbooks, electronic information education resources and other didactic materials, educational and methodological manuals, laboratory equipment, etc.) and educational technologies (educational methods, organizational forms, etc.) in the preparation of a specialist, that is, the formation and development of professional competencies a qualification practice is organized in order to carry out professional and pedagogical activities and carry out theoretical knowledge and practical skills obtained in the audience in ideal conditions from experience in real conditions. Reflexive practice of students in the process of studying Pedagogical Sciences (in various forms of active, contextual education) and according to the results of research work emotional emotional-value and assessment relations in relation to the process of interaction in the process of facts, material, education it is organized for the purpose of identification.

RESULTS

The theoretical analysis of the nature of professional competence, the modeling of its content, the development of the concept of reflexive monitoring of the formation of professional competence of students of a higher educational institution makes it possible to smoothly substantiate the advanced hypothesis. Experimental perspective in the review, hypothetically, the technology of reflexive monitoring of the formation of professional competence of students of a higher educational institution is effective if the following is laid down on the basis of its design and implementation:

- appropriate adequate forms of content-appropriate self-assessment and reflexive diagnosis of the formation of professional competence on the basis of quality benchmark in the process of studying Pedagogical Sciences of students and practically working employees;

- the interaction of management levels, goal orientations (strategic, tactical, operational), stages and management and implementation of targeted management programs by implementing the didactic foundations of the formation of professional competence of an educator in the logic of building a tree of goals.

To this end, we are faced with the task of solving the following tasks:

- experimental program development;
- conducting an empirical study specially organized to verify the effectiveness of the developed technology of reflexive monitoring of the formation of professional competence of students of a higher educational institution;
- the validity of the experimental data obtained;

The results achieved justification of reliability and validity of the methods used.

DISCUSSION

In order to successfully carry out his activities in all situations, the teacher constantly improves his knowledge and skills, regularly studies modern pedagogical and information technologies, advanced foreign pedagogical experiences, methods and methods, and pedagogical professional knowledge and skills. and will have personal qualities and will develop the necessary competencies during his practical activity. The methodology of carrying out any scientific research is expressed in the interpretation of the essence of the phenomenon and process being studied on the basis of the selected ideas, theories and approaches, the ideas about the object are modeled, the mechanisms of its effective development, tools and pedagogical conditions -conditions are determined. Professional competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level. Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to use it in one's work. Professional competence is clearly manifested in the following situations: - in complex processes and performing unclear tasks; - using conflicting information; - in order to have a plan of action in an unexpected situation, a specialist with professional competence first of all: - consistently enriches his knowledge and integrates new information; - deeply understands the requirements of the time and seeks new knowledge; - he can rework them and use them effectively in his practical work.

Organization and development of cooperative work of subjects in the further improvement of pedagogical processes, the effectiveness of developing their activity in the system of goals and tasks that are important to achieve, in every way depends on existing motives and motivation. The field of education is a social institution that reflects all the problems of society. It is necessary to enrich and improve spiritual and educational values in modern education, to humanize it through educational activities, to activate educational activities with spiritual and educational growth, and through pedagogical and psychological support. it is necessary to educate highly moral, responsible, creative, competent persons. Raising a person from the spiritual and educational side is an important issue of education today, and for this it is important that the teacher himself has a high level of spiritual and educational competence. Spirituality is a manifestation of qualities related to the enrichment of the inner world, aimed at opening up one's personal potential. Spirituality is a description of self-awareness as a person, reflecting perfection and balance of the

inner world. It is necessary to convey clear visions of spirituality, which is the main criterion for our material and spiritual growth, to the next generation. Spiritual and educational development is self-creation and development as a form of behavior directed towards oneself and others. The development of spiritual-educational competence is formed during personal development, the existence of a spiritual-educational role model (in the form of parents, teachers), and the organization of an educational process based on universal human values integrated into the educational program. Spiritual and educational growth - a person's assimilation of sources of religious and national values, traditional moral norms and spiritual ideals towards himself, those around him, the state and the world in general; it is carried out through educational tools in the organized educational process. The spiritual sources of spirituality are based on love for a person, success in life and high values. Scientific activity of teachers - searching for news, learning and basing on them and using scientifically proven sources, mastering the pedagogical, psychological and socio-economic bases of organizing and managing pedagogical processes, as well as applying innovative approach technologies to pedagogical processes defines tasks. In conclusion, we must say that introducing future teachers to various methods and methods of organizing and managing pedagogical processes, further developing their professional competence, arming them with the secrets of professional development, and forming a methodology for working with pedagogical innovations will increase the effectiveness of education. is one of the important increasing factors. In order to ensure the effectiveness of pedagogical processes, future teachers should have knowledge of strategic planning, design, modeling of pedagogical processes, coordination of student activities and ensuring their activity, methods, methods and principles of pedagogical process management according to situations, innovative technologies and based on them, it is necessary to develop the skills of organizing innovative activities of the subjects of the pedagogical process.

CONCLUSION

The main goal of modern education is to prepare a person who is fully developed for society and the state, socially adaptable to society and work, and who can work on himself. Therefore, the level of competence of pedagogues is important in education of a comprehensively developed personality. In the process of education and training, young people acquire the knowledge, manners, customs, culture and labor skills collected by their ancestors, take their rightful place in society based on life experience, and the personality of a pedagogue in the formation of their potential and outlook. It is no exaggeration to say that his professional skills are important

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